

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M4.1 First Living Lab Guiding Problem Identification and System Characterization

VERSION 1.1

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies, located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to establish efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The objective of this document is to report on the process of conducting the first living lab in Konya, Turkey. The aim of the living lab was to identify problems in the basing with stakeholders and determine the system characterization.

1. Introduction

This is the documentation of M4.1 of the “Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean” Grant Agreement Number 1923 project.

This document provides information on the intellectual basis, organization, implementation and outcomes of the milestone M4.1 “First Living Lab guiding problem identification and system characterization”.

The purpose of the first living lab (M4.1) held on the 30th of September in Konya city centre was to arrive at a mutual understanding of the “wicked” problem of groundwater unsustainability in the region and make a preliminary assessment of the mainstream proposed solutions. The workshop structure, as the WP4 on “Innovative governance and socio-economic assessment in the MED” built on the participatory methodology of “group model building” or “community-based system dynamics”.

After two rounds of field work, one held on March 2021 and the other in July 2021, which were designed to build and understand the community bases of the participatory activity in WP4, the M4.1 brought 26 people related to groundwater governance and management issues in Konya Closed Basin, from governmental, civil and business organizations.

Following the best practice published in Sciptapedia and methodological guidelines elsewhere, the M4.1 started with a presentation activity, followed by divergent activities and concluded with a convergent activity. In total, the four activities held in breakout groups of six aimed at first, building trust to work as the “living lab” of participatory systems modelling that will take us through the next steps during the almost two years of scientific work in the region. Secondly it served building a common language as the community identified their problems. Thirdly, it served identifying the projected futures and suggested policies. Lastly, the M4.1 concluded by exercising on conceptual mapping of the problem narratives that were elicited during the day.

In overall, the outcomes of M4.1, the “trust”, “problems and expectations mapped on specific time horizons” and the “seed conceptual maps” are going to serve as the basis of a second workshop M4.2 solely on conceptual mapping, as a continuation of the Konya Living Lab and the scientific activity of participatory systems modelling and analysis spanning whole through in WP4.

2. Methodology

The methodology is built on Group Model Building (Vennix, 1996) and Community Based System Dynamics (Howmand, 2014). Group Model Building method is mainly used for eliciting knowledge starting from problem identification to conceptualization, validation and analysis and used as a learning activity which enhances social learning process. In this project, the choice of methodology also aims to increase chances of implementation of results, as the problem, process and solutions are embraced by those who are in position to decide and act accordingly.

The literature in group model building has defined roles such as facilitator, modeler (reflector), process coach, recorder, conveners and specific scripts have been developed (Andersen and Richardson 1997, Hovmand et al. 2011).

Community based system dynamics (CBSD) is a participatory method for involving communities in the process of understanding and changing systems from endogenous or feedback perspective of system dynamics. This method builds on group model building, enhances community engagement and empowerment for collaborative problem solving. CBSD is in parallel to the idea of living labs.

2.1. Living Lab for the Konya Closed Basin, Turkey Case Study

The workshop for Konya Closed Basin case study was held on September 30th, 2021.

Groundwater is a vital resource for the basin, therefore, the continuous decrease in groundwater table is worrisome and requires attention from all stakeholders. That being so, the participatory workshop aimed to identify and discuss multiple aspects of groundwater-related issues, elicit stakeholder expectations for the future, propose solutions, and by doing so, develop the conceptual structure of the models that we (the project team and the stakeholders) will benefit from. The objective of the workshop sessions in general was to benefit from their knowledge and elicit their understanding of the subject.

26 people from different sectors and institutions participated in the workshop. The common ground of all participants was groundwater, whether they directly benefit from it, are responsible for protecting it, or do scientific research on it.

After the conceptual model was fully translated into the computer in Stella Architect, the participants were encouraged to come up with questions that they can ‘ask the model’. For example, in the model outputs the participants saw that adopting high-yield irrigation technologies or cultivating crops with lower water requirement would result in slower decrease in available groundwater.

Figure 2. The barrel analogy – to explain how available groundwater increases and decreases

Figure 3. The example model built for the 1st session

Following a brief introduction of how models are constructed and what they do, we moved on to the second session. Starting from the second session, the participants were divided to 4

groups of 6-7 people and each group was joined by a member of the research team as the group facilitator.

2nd SESSION

In the second session, each group started with a discussion on the factors that are perceived as fundamental to the decrease in groundwater table. With the help of group facilitators, each group drew graphs of how these factors changed over time. At the end of the session, one participant from each group presented their work to everyone and briefly explained the issues they discussed with their group.

Figure 4. A participant presenting his group's work at the end of the 2nd session

Figure 5. Exemplary outputs from 2nd session

The second session revealed that increase in irrigated land and cultivation of green plants are considered fundamental in groundwater decrease and increase in energy and other agricultural production costs. Increase in irrigation duration, adoption of high-yield irrigation technology and increase in cattle farming were also discussed in this session.

3rd SESSION

In the third session, the groups continued their discussion from the second session by showing their anticipations in business as usual scenario and their wishes (desires) for the future on the graphs. Participants also suggested solutions to achieve the desired future which they expressed on the graph. As in the second session, all groups presented their work to the whole plenary at the end of the session.

Figure 6. Exemply outputs from 3rd session (The black/blue lines represent the anticipation for business as usual scenario and the green lines represent desired states subject to solution suggestions)

In business as usual scenario, the common expectations were that the total irrigated land area and maize-cultivated land area will increase, the groundwater level will further decrease, and the costs of agricultural production will further increase. We also saw that the number of actively used groundwater wells and yearly irrigation duration were expected to increase.

On the same graphs, the participants expressed their desires with the green lines. The participants anticipated that if total irrigated land area was somehow balanced and farmers preferred to cultivate cereals instead of green plants – especially maize, the decrease in groundwater table could be stopped. They also emphasized the importance of preventing uncontrolled increase in the number of groundwater wells, reusing wastewater for irrigation, and inter-basin water transfer projects.

The solutions suggested by the participants in this session are summarized as follows:

- The importance of cooperation among various public authorities for the management of water resources was emphasized.
- The importance of information-based groundwater management and irrigation was emphasized; new irrigation technology options were mentioned.
- Using wastewater for irrigation, rainwater harvesting, and inter-basin water transfer options were discussed to increase available water resources.
- The necessity for state subventions to decrease agricultural input costs and state aids for traditional crops (cereals) instead of green plants was emphasized.

After the third session, we moved on to the fourth and last session where the groups discussed the causal relationships related to the issues discussed in the previous sessions.

4th SESSION

In the fourth session, the issues discussed in the previous sessions were approached from the perspective of cause-effect relationships and the groups drew causal map diagrams.

For example, one might argue that when the focus is the decrease in available groundwater level, groundwater extraction is a cause and increase in groundwater pumping energy cost is an effect. The increase in energy cost would result in decrease in agricultural water use (Figure 8, the upper loop). On the other hand, the decrease in groundwater table would result in increased demand for deeper groundwater wells. In response, the drilling of new and deeper wells would be expected to increase the agricultural water use again (Figure 8, lower loop).

Figure 7: A simple causal loop diagram

Figure 8. Group discussion during the 4th session

Each group had a similar discussion; below are two examples of the conceptual map diagrams drawn by two groups.

Figure 9. Exemplary conceptual maps from 4th session

Following the 4th session and the conceptual mapping exercise, the workshop was concluded with a conversation on the next steps.

The participants were assured that workshop discussions were not to be shared on any media and that their participation was individual, not on behalf of the institutions they belong to. That the objective of the workshop was to achieve a collective learning was emphasized.

Figure 10. Group photo at the end of the workshop

3. References

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